

SPORTS FOR HEALTH

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Abstract: *The article discusses the issues of the state of physical health of modern society, notes the negative dynamics of these changes. The reasons for the decrease in the quality of life are indicated, as well as possible ways to improve health by means of physical culture and sports are proposed.*

Keywords— health, lifestyle, motivation, nutrition, physical culture, sports.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the 21st century, the topic of a healthy lifestyle is indisputably relevant. Now this problem is gaining more and more popularity, since the tendencies of the deterioration of the environment, the replacement of natural products with synthetics, the rhythm of modern life negatively affect the health of people. By health, the World Health Organization understands a state of complete physical, social and mental well-being, in this regard, it is obvious that every person throughout his life has faced health problems to one degree or another. Sport is a good complex medicine for solving not all, but many of these problems. The concept of sports includes: health promotion; mastering the knowledge of the basics of physical culture and a healthy lifestyle; achieving an optimal level of physical qualities. In addition to the influence on the physical side of a person's development, sport contributes to the development of a person's psychological readiness for professional activity (enthusiasm, internal stamina and confidence in achieving the set goal) [1].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to statistics, annually over 300 people are recognized as disabled due to osteoporosis. Of these, 76% are people of working age. In order to prevent this disease, it is necessary to deal with a sedentary lifestyle [2]. Osteoporosis is not the only disease that can occur due to inactivity. Along with it, there is also a risk of cardiovascular pathology, obesity, insomnia and sleep disorders, neurosis-like disorders, cerebrovascular accidents, etc. To maintain and strengthen their health, doctors recommend spending time on physical activity and turning to sports, since it has a beneficial effect on human body. In the process of moderate physical exertion, the following occurs: 1) Strengthening of the musculoskeletal system - bones become more resistant to stress, muscle strength indicators develop, oxygen muscle nutrition improves; 2) Improvement of the cardiovascular system - the

heart and blood vessels become more resilient, quickly get used to stress and quickly recover from them; 3) Increasing immunity and improving blood composition - with regular exercise, the level of red blood cells and lymphocytes increases, which allows the body to get sick less often and cope much faster with viruses and bacteria; 4) Strengthening and development of the nervous system - speed, dexterity increases, coordination of movement improves and new conditioned reflexes are formed, as a result, the speed of nervous processes also develops; 5) Improvement of metabolism - there is an effective regulation of the content of sugar and other substances in the blood; 6) Improving the functioning of the respiratory system - due to the body's need for oxygen, breathing becomes intense and deeper, the vital capacity of the lungs increases; 7) Changing attitudes towards life - physical activity contributes to the formation of a stimulus in people in life, reduction of depression, irritability, exclusion of sudden mood swings [3].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order to avoid the occurrence of many diseases, as well as to improve your health, you must choose a suitable sport. There are many types of sports for all ages and preferences: 1) Swimming - this sport is ideal for women, because in the process muscles are tightened, while you do not feel fatigue, in addition, water is a subject of relaxation and allows you to calm the nervous system. 2) Jogging - useful in case of uniform movement and maintaining the speed of running, this sport has a good effect on the figure, blood supply improves. 3) Cycling - allows you to pump up the calf muscles, strengthen and acquire a beautiful shape of the buttocks, improve blood supply.

4) Jumping rope is the simplest and most effective means of maintaining shape, regular exercise can improve blood supply, but this sport is contraindicated for people with vascular diseases of the legs and heart failure. 5) Skiing is a useful winter sport, since fresh air and even physical activity have a positive effect on strengthening the muscle corset and

improving blood circulation. 6) Ice skating is another kind of winter sport that allows you to strengthen the muscles of the legs, develop plasticity and flexibility, the study of the elements of figure skating has a positive effect on the structure of the body shape and stability to maintain balance [4]. The variety of sports is not limited to this list. Each type is useful and interesting in its own way, in connection with which a person can try himself in any of them and choose the most suitable one. Sport has no age restrictions: even if an elderly person wants to go in for swimming or race walking, this will only have a beneficial effect on the body and bring lightness and vigor. The usefulness of sport is indisputable, but do not forget that excessive loads can have a negative effect on the body, so you do not need to exhaust yourself with daily long workouts. To maintain health, it is quite enough: - 30 minutes of interval training per week, which reduces the risk of developing diabetes; - 2.5 hours of any moderate-intensity physical activity that reduces the risk of developing cancer; - 3 hours of walking per week to help relieve symptoms of depression; - 7.5 hours of any kind of training per week, which will reduce the risk of premature death; - 2 hours of any moderate intensity aerobic exercise per week to improve concentration; - 1.5 hours of any workout to keep blood pressure normal [5]. Summing up, we can conclude that sport plays an important role in human life, its diversity contributes to diversified development and makes people more resistant to the negative factors of the surrounding world. Sports activity develops physical data, fosters character, hardens the body, makes a person strong and enduring, and most importantly, strengthens his health, which is an essential quality, since maintaining health is one of the main tasks of a person, especially in the modern world.

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, in addition to personal preferences in the organization of their physical activity, there are also state motives in increasing the physical working capacity of the population of the country, of all its strata. This is evidenced by the many promising laws of the field of physical culture and sports, adopted in the Uzbekistan recently. It is a completely justified aspiration, which, if successfully implemented, will bear fruit. Such as: the continuation of life, the efficiency of the productivity of the working-age population, an increase in the birth rate, etc. Definitely, this is a good and timely trend in our country - it is gaining momentum [6].

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